

Clustering Massive Packets using a Lock-Free Algorithm of Tree-Based Reduction on GPGPU

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Abstract— Recently, the inspection of huge traffic log is imposing a great burden on security analysts. Unfortunately, there have been few research efforts focusing on scalability in analysing very large PCAP file with reasonable computing resources. In this paper, we present Asura which is a huge PCAP analyzer using A Lock-Free Algorithm of Tree-Based Reduction on GPGPU. Asura’s parallel packet dump inspection is based on task-based decomposition and therefore can handle massive threads for large PCAP file without considering tidy parameter selection in adopting data decomposition. Asura is designed to scale out in processing large PCAP file by taking as many threads as possible. Asura takes two steps. First, Asura extracts feature vector represented by associative containers of $\langle \text{sourceIP}, \text{destIP} \rangle$ pair. By doing this, the feature vector can be drastically small compared with the size of original PCAP files. In other words, Asura can reduce packet dump data into the size of unique $\langle \text{sourceIP}, \text{destIP} \rangle$ pairs (for example, in experiment, Asura’s output which is reduced in first step is about 2a parallel clustering algorithm is applied for the feature vector which is represented as $\langle \text{sourceIP}, \text{destIP} \rangle, V[i]$ where $V[i]$ is aggregated flow vector. In second step, Asura adopts an enhanced Kmeans algorithm. Concretely, two functions of Kmeans which are (1)calculating distance and (2)relabeling points are improved for parallel processing.

Also, Asura uses a Lock-free technique of tree-based reduction for large scale clustering on GPGPU. Proposal method is divided into two steps: fine reduction and coarse reduction. In the first reduction step, the clustering program obtain $K * N$ intermediate array where K is the number of clusters and N is the number of blocks. In the following step, new mean value is calculated over N blocks. By doing this, the clustering program can evade using atomic instruction which causes lock contention in coping with large scale clusters. In experiment, the performance of native GPU kernel with atomic instruction, Thrust template libraries and proposal method is compared and evaluated. For your paper to be published in the conference proceedings, you must use this document as both an instruction set and as a template into which you can type your own text. If your paper does not conform to the required format, you will be asked to fix it.

(Abstract)

Keywords-component; Clustreing; Massive Packets; Lock-free Algorithm, Tree-based Reduction, GPGPU

I. INTRODUCTION

The scale of network traffic are growing year by year. Besides, as the emergence of sophisticated cyber attack such as APT (Advanced Persistent Threat), we are forced to cope with the detailed packet inspection as well as checking other traffic logs. Currently, the inspection of huge traffic log is imposing a great burden on security analysts. Traffic irregularities or traffic anomalies is usually described as the result of one or more occurrences which changes the normal flow of data. Anomaly detection is the process of finding patterns in the audit network traffic log which do not conform to legitimate or normal behavior. The design of an anomaly detection method relies on a baseline model which represents the normal behavior of network traffic. The model is generally trained using audit data extracted from traffic for which all items are labeled in advance as either normal or anomalous. However, labelling traffic data is often expensive and time-consuming partly because it requires human experts.

II. OVERVIEW

A. Task-based decomposition

If we want to transform code into a concurrent version, there are two ways. First one is data decomposition, in which the program cope with a large collection of data and can compute every chunk of the data independently. Second one is task decomposition, in which the process is partitioned into a set of independent tasks that threads can execute in any order. Data decomposition has some drawbacks. For example, the size of PCAP file varies according to the situation in which the file is dumped. Besides each divided process is NOT homogeneous. Asura adopts task-based parallel processing which is shown in Figure1. Asura’s parallel packet dump inspection is based on task-based decomposition and therefore can handle massive threads for large PCAP file without considering tidy parameter selection in adopting data decomposition. Asura is designed to scale out in processing large PCAP file by taking as many threads as possible. Assume that we have n threads and each thread and each thread is

associated with one PCAP file. By doing this, Asura can take advantages of dynamic scheduling for coping with a variety of kinds and size of PCAP file. Asura consists of two thread sets: a master thread which enqueues the name of PCAP file and a worker thread which processes the each PCAP file. The master thread enqueues the list of PCAP file, and passes it to the worker thread. More specifically, the master thread traverses PCAP file directory and enqueue the file name. When the queue is full, the master thread waits until the worker thread processing packets consumes a file name and removes it from the queue. The worker (packet processing thread) dequeues a file name and parses the PCAP file. The task of the worker thread is flow vector aggregation using associative container discussed later in III-A.

Fig. 1. Task Decomposition

B. Features selection and structures

In general, most system of the identification of anomalies on traffic volume is based on features. The features could be many: source and destination addresses, port numbers, static signatures, statistics signatures and so on. The difficulty of the anomaly traffic identification is to handle the huge traffic volume. The challenging part here is to select which header item are worth and suitable to be learned. For simplicity, we pick up the five items as follows:

- Source and destination IP addresses: unique identifiers of sender and receiver.
- The number of captured packets: the fields is reflected by the traffic volume.
- TLEN (total length of packets): the 16-bit field defines the entire packet volume in bytes, including both header and data.
- TTL (The time-to-live): the time-to-live value can be referred as an upper bound on the time which an IP datagram can be processed.
- source and destination port: port number is checked for the type of application.

Structure is shown as follows. For each fields, the numerical fields of packet header are reduced using

associative container of map < key, value >. The key stores number of packets. In other words,

```
1: /* STRUCTURE II: reduced */
2: typedef struct _reduced {
3:   map<int, int> count;
4:   map<int, int> tlen;
5:   map<int, int> ttl;
6:   map<int, int> sport;
7:   map<int, int> dport;
8:   pthread_mutex_t mutex;
9: } reduced_t;
10: reduced_t reduced;
```

Another challenging part is to transform code into a concurrent version with massive multithreading. For reduction, we use the structure as follows.

```
1: /* STRUCTURE I: srcIP, destIP */
2: typedef struct _addrpair {
3:   map<string, string> m;
4:   pthread_mutex_t mutex;
5: } addrpair_t;
6: addrpair_t addrpair;
```


Fig. 2. Flow vector computation by multithreading

Here pthread mutex t is the notation for mutual execution. Mutual exclusion locks (mutexes) prevent multiple threads from simultaneously executing critical sections of code which access shared data (that is, mutexes are used to serialize the execution of threads). All mutexes must be global. Threads within the same process or within other processes can share mutexes. Mutexes can synchronize threads within the same process or in other processes. Mutexes can be used to synchronize threads between processes if the mutexes are allocated in writable memory and shared among the cooperating processes and have been initialized for this task.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Extracting feature vector using associative container

Associative containers are a generic group of class templates in the standard library of the C++ programming language which cope with ordered associative arrays. The containers are

the shortest distance. Once the shortest distance is figured out and the new cluster is assigned, this reduction module calculates new_sum_x , new_sum_y according to the new clusters.

Fire reduction is divided into two loops. Besides, first loop has one branch and second loop is two branches. First loop aims to calculate the shortest distance for the nearest cluster of each point and assign the new cluster to the point. Second loop aims to calculate the new sum of each cluster (K). First branch at line 28-31 is responsible for the reduction for each block. Second branch at line 33-37 is responsible for terminate condition. If the $local_index$ is 0, this means final reduced value is stored to $new_sums_x[cluster_index]$.

Fig. 5. Data representation of coarse reduction. After the fine reduction, the input data size is $N * M$ where N is the number of blocks and M is the number of clusters.

C. Coarse Reduction Pattern

Once the fine reduction is done, the next step is to obtain $K*N$ sequences where K is the number of cluster and N is the number of blocks as shown in Figure 5. Coarse reduction figures out the sum of data points for each cluster. Note that the program performs the assignment and block-wise reduction in the same kernel. Then, the program invokes a coarse reduction to sum the block-wise values into a final, single value: Recall that in the fine reduction step, each block produces one sum per cluster. As such, you can visualize the input to the coarse reduction like this: The goal is to combine all these values into k sums, by summing up the individual, block-wise cluster sums (i.e. have one sum for each k_i). To do so, the program simply stop the reduction at stride k , as you can see in the code above. Figure 3 shows the data representation of coarse reduction. At the beginning of coarse reduction, the program have $K*N$ array where K is the number of cluster and N is the the number of blocks.

V. EXPERIMENT

A. Case1: Atomic Instructions

By using the `atomicAdd` function, programmer can rewrite the `incr` kernel. This instruction atomically add a value $V[i]$ to the value stored at memory location M . The updated `incr` kernel adopts a statement to increment the value stored at the

location pointer P . Then the instruction below return the values saved at pointer P before the increment operation.

```
__global__ void incr(__global__ int *ptr) { int temp = atomicAdd( ptr, 1); }
```

B. Case2: CUDA Thrust Template Library

CUDA Thrust is a C++ template library based on the Standard Template Library (STL). Thrust makes is possible to implement high performance parallel applications with reasonable effort by a high-level application interface. Thrust has a rich collection of data parallel primitives such as scan, sort, and reduce. Thrust provides two vector containers, `host_vector` and `device_vector`. The `host_vector` is stored in host memory while `device_vector` lives in GPU device memory. Many of algorithms provided by Thrust direct analogs in the STL.

C. Case3: Fine-Coarse Reduction

Reductions in serial execution like the averaging performed during the update step scale linearly. However, parallel reductions can be implemented efficiently by using two-stage tree-reduction: fine and coarse reduction. Key point in fine-coarse reduction is averaging is not performed over all our data. Instead, for each cluster, the points assigned to each cluster should be averaged. There are a few tricks for solving this problem. For doing this, the program can sort the data by their assignment, so that points in the same cluster are next to each other in memory. Then program can do one standard reduction per segment by decreasing the stride.

Fig. 6. Computing time with respect to the number of iterations. At the number of iterations 175, proposed method (fine-coarse) is about 2-4 times faster.

D. Reduction

Figure 6 show a comparison of algorithms of case 1, case 2 and case 3 in performing K-Means. In experiment, the scalability of proposed three algorithms is investigated in the case where the number of iterations is increasing. As data size constant with scaling the number of iterations remains the same, it is observed that proposed method of fine-coarse reduction outperforms two other algorithms.

Figure 7 displays comparison of computing time concerning the number of data points. The comparison of case 1, case2 and case 3 in running K-means is depicted. It turns to be clear that case 1 (atomic) and case 3 (fine-coarse) keeps the constant while the case 2 (thrust) is increasing linearly.

Fig. 7. Computing time with respect to the number of data points. During the iteration 1-175, proposed method remains constant computing time.

VI. RELATED WORK

Clustering which is grouping of similar objects [1] is one of the most popular procedures in data mining [2]. There are many practical applications of clustering such as unsupervised classification and taxonomy generation [3], nearest neighbor searching [4], scientific discovery [5], vector quantization [6], time series analysis [7], and multidimensional visualization [8,9,10]. However, there have been few research efforts in the view point of a large scale graph mining. There are many research efforts on parallelizing data mining algorithms such as association rules and classification. To name a few, Agrawal and Shafer [11], Chatratchat et al. [12], Cheung and Xiao [13], Han, Karypis, and Kumar [14]. Based on these works., the thrust of our paper is that how to parallelize edge contraction is focused. There are two main approaches for making Kmeans able to cluster very large datasets. The first approach is based on sampling and coresets extraction. A coreset is a small set of instances that is representative of the properties of the original data[15]. The second approach is to modify Kmeans to reduce resource utilization and scalability[16]. The third approach is applying preprocess such as PCA and dimension reduction before clustering process[17]. Compared with these research efforts, the novelty of our paper is the proposal of an effective pre-processing of a large scale graph clustering using parallel edge contraction.

Clemens et al. propose an approach for centroid update by combining point assignment and centroid updating [18]. A study of synchronization strategies mainly concerning concurrent data structures is shown in [19]. Zechner et al. propose parallelizing the distance calculation on GPU [20]. Lock-based synchronization scheme which allows lock stealing

within individual warps is proposed in [21]. Xu et al. propose software transactional memory leveraged by a hierarchical validation and encounter-time lock-sorting mechanism [22].

Concurrency and synchronization is important research topic in parallelism. In [23], a large empirical study of the concurrent behavior of deployed GPUs is conducted. [24] propose a technique for measurement and analysis of lock contention which processes data associated with locks about the idleness of spinning threads. Pan et al. present a method for allowing predicting the contention under the queue delegation locking algorithm [25]. In [26], Daniel et al. present a systematic research of synchronization strategies, mainly focusing on concurrent data structures.

VII. CONCLUSION

Recently, the inspection of huge traffic log is imposing a great burden on security analysts. Unfortunately, there have been few research efforts focusing on scalability in analyzing very large PCAP file with reasonable computing resources. Asura is full-scratch (and painful) implementation with POSIX Pthreads and C++ STL. PCAP files are NOT organized in a regular pattern or the parsing of PCAP files is different or unpredictable for each element in the stream. Leveraging Pthreads which represents assembly language in parallelism provides maximum flexibility. Asura adopts taskbased implementation for processing huge, heterogeneous and unpredictable PCAP file stream.

Asura the lock-free algorithm of tree-based reduction for evading the lock contention which causes the serious speed down in concurrent programming. Proposal method is divided into two steps: fine reduction and coarse reduction. In the first reduction step, the program obtain $K * N$ intermediate array where K is the number of clusters and N is the number of blocks. In the following step, new mean value is calculated over N blocks. Proposal method enables us to avoid using atomic instruction which causes lock contention in coping with large scale clusters. In experiment, the performance of native GPU kernel with atomic instruction, Thrust template libraries and proposal method is compared and evaluated. Proposal method is adopted for K-Means which processes the large number of data points. It has become clear that proposal method outperforms the conventional method with the atomic instruction in scaling both the number of data points and iterations. There are many discussions about the drawback of lock contention in both multi-core CPU and GPGPU.

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